

A Heterogeneous Precipitate based Ion Selective Electrode for Calcium

R. C. MISRA** and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA*

Electrochemical Sensor Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 21 April 1995, revised 19 February 1996, accepted 4 March 1996

A number of different types of ion selective electrodes for Ca^{II} ion are known¹. Calcium gives precipitate with sodium rhodizonate and this precipitate has been used for developing a sensor for rhodizonate ion². Rhodizonates of Ba and Ca have also been used as electroactive materials for the preparation of Sr and Ba sensors³. Here, preparation of Ca^{II} ion sensor using calcium(II) rhodizonate as electroactive material has been reported.

Results and Discussion

A series of standard solutions (1×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-6} M) of CaCl_2 was prepared and the potential was recorded with the prepared electrode using a Philips PR 9405 potentiometer at room temperature ($19 \pm 1^\circ$). A linear response in potential vs concentration plot was obtained upto 1×10^{-6} M with a slope of 30 mV per decade change in Ca^{II} ion concentration. Other properties determined were response time (12 s), effect of pH (working pH range 2.0–11.0) and age of the membrane (36 weeks). The selectivity coefficients for different cations determined by mixed solution method⁴ were as follows: Ba^{II} , Mg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} , 0.1; Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} and Hg^{II} , 0.01.

Fig. 1. Plots of potential vs volume of titrant: (A) Na-carbonate, (B) Na-oxalate, (C) Na-tungstate and (D) Na-tetraphenylborate.

Application: To see the utility of the electrode prepared the electrode was used as an indicator electrode in the precipitation titration of CaCl_2 with $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$. Electrode potential of CaCl_2 solution (0.01 M, 5 ml) made up to 20 ml by double-distilled water) was measured. This solution was titrated against 0.01 M $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ potentiometrically. Electrode potentials were plotted against the volume of $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ solution consumed. Similar titrations of CaCl_2 against Na_2CO_3 , Na_2WO_3 and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{BNa}$ were also performed and in these cases too the inflexion points correspond to the expected equivalence points (Fig. 1).

Experimental

To a dilute solution (50 ml) of CaCl_2 was added a dilute solution of sodium rhodizonate which was made basic with 1 M NaOH. The resulting dirty white solid of calcium rhodizonate⁵ was washed with double-distilled water and dried in air at room temperature. Then master membrane was prepared by mixing the solid (100 mg) with epoxy resin (400 mg)⁶.

A small portion from the master membrane was fixed at one end of a glass tube (o.d. 0.8 cm, i.d. 0.5 cm) with araldite and the tube was filled with 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution. A saturated calomel electrode was inserted in the tube for electrical contact. A separate saturated calomel electrode was used as external reference electrode,

Before taking measurement the membrane of the electrode was kept immersed for 6 days in 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to State Council of Science and Technology, U.P., for financial assistance.

References

1. R. M. GARRELS, M. SATO, M. E. THOMPSON and A. H. TRUESDELL, *Science*, 1962, **135**, 1045; A. S. KAY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, **39**, 1056; J. W. ROSS, JR., *Science*, 1967, **156**, 1378; G. J. MOODY, R. B. OKE and J. D. R. THOMOS, *Analyst*, 1972, **97**, 420; J. RUZICKA and E. H. HANSEN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **67**, 155; D. JAGNER and J. P. OSTERGAARD-JENSON, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **80**, 9; D. AMMAN, M. GUGGI, E. PRETSCH and W. SIMON, *Anal. Lett.*, 1975,

**Present address: Conservation Laboratory, Allahabad Museum, Allahabad.

NOTE

8. 709; L. KEIL, G. J. MOODY and J. D. R. THOMAS, *Analyst*, 1977, **102**, 274; J. D. R. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1986, 1135.
2. N. ARORA and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *J. Inst. Chem. India*, 1989, **61**, 12.
3. N. FAIZAN and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *J. Inst. Chem. India*, 1990, **62**, 95; R. C. MISRA and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 229.
4. G. J. MOODY and J. D. R. THOMAS, *Talanta*, 1971, **18**, 1251.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1969.
6. R. C. MISRA and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **27**, 1011.